

Testing the Fiery Mantis Myth

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Abstract. Despite enduring and varied Southern African folkloric accounts of the praying mantis’s ability to spread fire, no research was found to have explored the validity of these claims. This study tested, under controlled conditions, whether mantis wings — and wings of other insect species — could retain fire, and whether they can transport fire. We tested the fire retention capabilities of eight insect species using two experimental approaches: direct wing burning and exposing flying insects to a fire zone. The first method demonstrated that while the wings of *Tenodera sinensis* Saussure, 1871 and *Acrida cinerea* (Thunberg, 1815), were able to retain fire for about 2 seconds, other species exhibited significantly lower flame retention. Although the second method did not yield conclusive evidence on the ability of insects to fly or jump with burning wings, our findings suggest that certain insects, such as the male *sinensis*, whose light body and powerful leap can carry it quite far even without flying, may plausibly spread fire. While this study does not definitively support the fire-spreading mantis myth, it provides preliminary evidence that certain Mantodea and orthoptera species, under specific conditions, may plausibly carry fire. To the best of our knowledge, this research is the first attempt to scientifically investigate the potential fire spreading capabilities of insect wings, highlighting the need for further studies, particularly with species native to Southern Africa, and opening avenues for future research into insect wings and flight capabilities under extreme conditions, with broad implications across multiple fields.

The praying mantis has captured the imagination of various cultures around the world, often being depicted with extraordinary powers and symbolism. Among the most curious of these tales are those originating in Southern Africa’s Khoisan¹ cultures. The belief that the mantis has divine powers was perhaps first documented in 1719 (Kolben, 1719) and in the English language by 1874 (Bleek, 1875). Stories have flourished since, telling that the mantis can spread fire. These narratives continue to influence indigenous groups to this day when one finds that the Sesotho word for mantis, *sechesa-ntlo*, translates into English as “house-burner” (Google Translate, 2024).

Is the praying mantis incendiary? The Khoisan stories associating the mantis with fire tell that the mantis has been feared and loved as a God (Theal, 1919); that it stole fire and gave it to the people (Lewis-Williams, 2016), like Prometheus; that the mantis can control fire (Lynch & Roberts, 2010); can pass through it alive (Scheub, 2012); that it represents lightning (Ki-Zerbo, 1990); and that it can also cause fires (African Wildlife, 1946).

¹ Modern term to refer collectively to the San bushmen and Khoekhoe pastoralist peoples

The first author reports verbal accounts from people living in Eswatini that mantises are feared there, especially when there is a fire in the vicinity of thatched huts, because it is believed that these insects have the ability to carry flames on its wings during flight, landing on grass houses and setting them ablaze.

Despite the endurance of these folkloric accounts through centuries, and the widely studied insect wing nanostructures, no scientific effort was found to verify this myth. Considering the relatively straightforward nature of testing this hypothesis, at least on the basic level attempted by this study, it is surprising that it has not been examined before, despite wing nanostructures having been widely studied. The inquiry is not superfluous given the numerous discoveries in which tales of creatures, like the *werewolf* and the *kraken*, were found to have a basis in real, albeit sometimes exaggerated, biological phenomena. While some aspects of these myths may be purely allegorical, the notion of the mantises' interaction with fire presents yet another opportunity to explore the intersection between myth and reality. The role of indigenous knowledge in understanding species and their environmental interactions has gained increasing recognition in scientific research (Jessen et. al, 2021). Cognate studies about other animals intentionally spreading fire do exist, such as the documented fire-spreading behavior of Australian raptors like the Black Kite (*Milvus migrans* (Boddaert, 1783)) and Whistling Kite (*Haliastur sphenurus* (Vieillot, 1818)), believed to carry burning sticks to spread wildfires (Bonta et al., 2017).

Our study centers on examining whether the mantis wings could feasibly sustain sparks or flames on its wings, as well as maintain fire during flight, potentially offering a scientific explanation for these long-standing myths. By including a range of distinct insect species, the investigation aims to offer a broader understanding of the variability in fire retention capabilities of insect wings. While the findings are preliminary and not based on rigorous experimentation, this study represents the first contribution to exploring the potential for mantis wings to retain fire, suggesting that under certain conditions, insect wings may sustain and transport flames, thus offering a scientific foundation for the fire-related myths surrounding the praying mantis.

METHODS

All insects used in the experiment were adults, native to and sourced from Japan, and none were bred in captivity. Ethical concerns associated with burning living insects are acknowledged and steps were taken to minimize suffering and the number of insects killed in the experimental design. These steps included handling the insects carefully and ensuring that the tests were as brief and controlled as possible. While the primary focus was on the mantis, the study also tested other insect species to allow for a comparative analysis of fire-retention capabilities. Eight insect species from four different orders were included in the experiment:

Mantodea:

- *Tenodera sinensis* Saussure, 1871
- *Hierodula patellifera* Audinet-Serville, 1839

Orthoptera:

- *Shirakiacris shirakii* (Bolivar, 1914)
- *Formosatettix larvatus* Bey-Bienko, 1951
- *Acrida cinerea* (Thunberg, 1815)

Odonata:

- *Orthetrum albistylum* (Selys, 1848)

Lepidoptera:

- *Gonepteryx aspasia* Gistel, 1857
- *Papilio machaon* Linne, 1758

This selection was made to examine the fire-retention capabilities of a wide variety of insect wings, including those from different orders and distinct species within the same order. Two experimental methods were employed to investigate the insects' interaction with fire, the Wing Flammability Test and the Flight Through Fire Test.

Wing Flammability Test

The first method involved a direct flammability test conducted on wings removed from living, healthy specimens. The test focused on both forewings and hindwings of each species. Insects were carefully handled, and their wings were removed at the base using a pair of extra fine scissors for precision. The detached wings were then held with a pair of tweezers and extended as much as possible to ensure they were open, resembling their position during flight, to avoid burning it in a folded position.

Burning forewing of *Tenodera sinensis*.

The outstretched wings were then exposed to a flame from an ordinary long lighter. Each wing was burned from the tip, but only until it caught fire; the point at which the lighter was removed, and the wing was allowed to burn freely. The time taken for each wing to sustain the fire was recorded after ignition with a GoPro Hero10 HD action camera setup to capture the burning process in slow motion. A comparative analysis was conducted on how long each type of wing could sustain a flame. This test aimed to provide an initial understanding of the fire retention capacity of mantis wings and those of other insect species, for comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The duration for which each insect wing could sustain the fire was measured after ignition using slow-motion footage captured by the action camera at 240fps, with frame-by-frame analysis conducted in VLC Media Player. We categorized data according to species and wing type (forewing and hindwing) tested. Obviously, the flame retention capacity of insect wings varied significantly across species and wing types. The chart below illustrates the differences in how long the wings of each species sustained fire and allows for a comparison of the fire retention duration of forewings and hindwings across the insect species tested.

Among the Mantodea, the *Tenodera sinensis* specimen, unlike the *Hierodula patellifera* specimen, demonstrated a relatively high fire retention capacity, with forewings able to sustain the flame for 1.58 seconds, and causing the fire to subside before it consumes the wing completely, part of it remaining

green. Among Orthopterans, the forewing of the *Acrida cinerea* specimen, also the largest of all insects tested, retained flame the longest, 2.02 seconds, also burning only partially before the flame died out. In contrast with the Mantodea and Orthoptera, which partially remained intact, the Odonata and Lepidoptera species burned completely, turning black. The way the Odonata and Lepidoptera wings burned was notably different as well; they exhibited a more rapid, total combustion, akin to a string catching fire or a firework igniting, where the flames spread quickly across the entire wing until it was entirely burnt.

Comparison of flame retention durations across eight insect species. Each insect species corresponds to two columns: the first column represents the species forewings, and the second column the hindwings. The color gradation within each column illustrates the extent of burning observed: Red to black to green gradient = wings that burned partially, with the flame dying out before complete combustion, leaving part of the wing intact; Red to black gradient = wings that burned entirely, turning black. The Y-axis of the chart represents the time in seconds, ranging from 0.00 to 2.00 seconds, indicating how long each wing type from each insect species was able to sustain the flame after the fire source was removed. The X-axis labels the insect species tested.

Flight Through Fire Test

The second method aimed to test the myth of mantises spreading fire. A controlled setup was created to allow insects to fly into a fire source. This experiment also included mantises as well as other insect species. A wire mesh tube with larger holes was constructed to ensure clear camera visibility. A denser wire mesh tube, with roughly the same diameter and approximately half the length of the first, was inserted into the larger tube to prevent the insects from escaping.

Flight Through Fire Test experimental setup

The mesh tube was placed on top of a camping stove, positioned in the middle of the tube to generate the fire. When necessary, a leaf blower was used to force the insects to fly into the tube, from the end with the denser mesh towards the fire source. The insects' flight and their interaction with the fire were recorded using the same camera, set to slow motion for detailed observation. This method was used to determine whether mantises or other insects could sustain sparks or flames while in flight.

Although some preliminary data were collected in the second method, the results were insufficient for meaningful analysis due to several significant challenges in the experimental setup. The flight behavior of the insects was difficult to control, with many insects either flying in unpredictable directions or failing to enter the fire as intended. Some insects landed headfirst in the fire, others got stuck to the stove or the mesh, and a few escaped the tube altogether. Additionally, technical issues, such as the leaf blower inadvertently turning off the stove, repeatedly disrupted the experiment. The flames themselves obstructed the camera's visibility, making it challenging to clearly observe the insects' interactions with the fire. Furthermore, ethical concerns regarding the insects' suffering led to the decision to abandon this method.

LIMITATIONS

This study had several limitations that could be addressed in future research. One major limitation is the inability to test species of mantises and other insects sourced from South Africa regions relevant to the fire-spreading mantis beliefs. Further ethnographic studies are needed to identify the species most closely associated with the myth of the fire-spreading mantis in these regions. The Japanese insects used in this study may not exhibit the same characteristics, potentially limiting the generalizability and relevance of our findings.

Another limitation was the lack of expertise needed to understand the variance in the fire retention capacity based on physical and chemical properties of the wings — such as wing size, frame structure, texture, composition etc., factors that undoubtedly influence insect wings' ability to retain fire. For instance, a comparative analysis of the carbon and hydrogen content in the chemical composition of mantis and other insect species' wings that best sustain and/or suppress fire, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how these insects might contribute to fire propagation.

Additionally, ethical considerations aimed at minimizing the number of insects sacrificed resulted in the decision to test a single sample and a limited range of species. Given the inherent challenges in performing such a specialized experiment with limited expertise and resources, it is important to recognize that our study could hardly capture the complexity of the phenomena. To take one aspect alone, two specific limitations arose while employing our second method from our equipment's inability to capture the jumping and flight behavior of insects with burning wings: 1) it is known that mantises and grasshoppers initiate aerial escape through active jumping (Zhao et al., 2024). Our experimental setup was not designed to observe whether the insects could still propel themselves with their usual jump and perhaps even fly with burning wings; 2) additionally, we were unable to determine, using our equipment, whether the legs of these insects could still facilitate their known jumping distance (Sutton et al., 2016) after exposure to fire. If the legs were still functional, the insect could jump over short distances, such as onto a nearby straw hut, as described in the myth. This raises the possibility that, even if the wings were burning and impaired for flight, such insects may still be able to spread fire in a way not captured by this research.

Though the study is a significant first step, a more advanced experimental setup, including professional high-speed cameras and more precise controls, would likely offer more accurate results. It is hoped that future studies, utilizing more sophisticated equipment and refined methodologies, will expand upon this research, providing more reliable data on the potential fire-retention and fire-spreading capabilities of insect wings.

CONCLUSIONS

Although this study does not conclusively substantiate the centuries-old Khoisan stories about the “fiery” mantis, it presents preliminary evidence that certain species of Mantodea and Orthoptera — specifically *Tenodera sinensis* and *Acrida cinerea* — unlike other species of insects tested, are capable of sustaining flames for a duration which suggests that, under certain conditions, insects such as these, which both jump and fly, could plausibly spread fire.

The distinct burning patterns observed using our first method, direct wing burning, further highlight the variability in fire-retention capabilities across different insect groups, which remain to be studied. Species within Odonata and Lepidoptera exhibited more rapid and complete combustion, contrasting with the fire retention and suppression seen in Mantodea and Orthoptera, which can remain partially intact. The second experimental method, designed to test whether these insects could transport the fire on their wings, was inconclusive due to technical difficulties and ethical concerns. Additionally, the study's reliance on non-Southern African species, while providing some insights, limits the direct applicability of the results to the myth in question. Further research is needed, which should involve local South African mantis species, alongside advanced experimental techniques, to more accurately assess the fire-spreading capabilities of these insects. Exploring the role of mantises in myth and folklore through scientific inquiry may reveal new insights into the intersection between culture and nature, beneficial for both mankind and “mantiskind”.

REFERENCES

- African Wildlife (1946) South Africa. Wildlife Protection Society of Southern Africa.
BLEEK, W. H. I. (1875): A Brief Account of Bushman Folk-lore and Other Texts. Juta, United Kingdom.
BONTA, M., GOSFORD, R., EUSSEN, D., FERGUSON, N., LOVELESS, E. & WITWER, M. (2017):
Intentional fire-spreading by “Firehawk” raptors in Northern Australia. *Journal of Ethnobiology*,
37(4), 700-718.

- Google Translate (2024) Translation of sechesa-ntlo (Sesotho to English). Translation retrieved August 26, 2024. Available at: <https://translate.google.com/>
- JESSEN, T. D., BAN, N. C., CLAXTON, N. X. & DARIMONT, C. T. (2022): Contributions of Indigenous Knowledge to ecological and evolutionary understanding. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 20(2), 93-101.
- KI-ZERBO, J. (1990): *Methodology and African Prehistory*. J. Currey, UK.
- KOLBEN, P. & MEDLEY, G. (trans.) (1719): *Caput Bonae Spei hodiernum*; in English "The present state of the Cape of Good Hope: or, A particular account of the several nations of the Hottentots. " 2nd ed. W. Innys, London. Available at: <https://hdl.handle.net/2027/yale.39002003202505>
- LEWIS-WILLIAMS, J. D. (2016): *Myth and Meaning: San-Bushman Folklore in Global Context*. Taylor Francis, United Kingdom.
- LYNCH, P. A. & ROBERTS, J. (2010): *African Mythology, A to Z*. Infobase Holdings, Incorporated, United States.
- SCHEUB, H. (2012): *Trickster and Hero: Two Characters in the Oral and Written Traditions of the World*. University of Wisconsin Press, United States.
- SUTTON, G. P., DOROSHENKO, M., CULLEN, D. A. & BURROWS, M. (2016): 'Take-off speed in jumping mantises depends on body size and a power-limited mechanism', *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 219(14), pp. 2127–2136. doi: 10.1242/jeb.133728. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.133728>
- THEAL, G. M. (1919): *Ethnography and Condition of South Africa Before AD 1505*. George Allen Unwin, United Kingdom.
- ZHAO, X., LIU, J.-X., CHARLES-DOMINIQUE, T., CAMPOS-ARCEIZ, A., DONG, B., YAN, L., O'HANLON, J. C., ZENG, Y. & CHEN, Z. (2024): Petal-shaped femoral lobes facilitate gliding in orchid mantises. *Current Biology*, 34(1), pp. 183–189.e4. doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2023.11.003. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960982223015178>